

Gas phase detection of Chemical Warfare Agents CWAs with portable Raman

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Abstract

The development of SERS substrates for chemical detection of specific analytes requires appropriate selection of plasmonic metal and the surface where it is deposited. Here we deposited Ag nanoplates on three substrates: i) conventional SiO₂/Si wafer, ii) stainless steel mesh and iii) graphite foils. The SERS enhancement of the signal was studied for Rhodamine 6G (R6G) as common liquid phase probe molecule. We conducted a comprehensive study with $\lambda=532, 633$ and 785 nm on all the substrates. The best substrate was investigated, at the optimum laser 785 nm, for gas phase detection of dimethyl methyl phosphonate (DMMP), simulant of the G-series nerve agents, at a concentration of 2.5 ppmV (14 mg/m³). The spectral fingerprint was clearly observed; with variations on the relative intensities of SERS Raman bands compared to bulk DMMP in liquid phase reflects the DMMP-Ag interactions. These interactions were simulated by Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations and the simulated spectra matched with the experimental one. Finally, we were detected the characteristics DMMP fingerprint with hand-held portable equipment. These results open the way for the application of SERS technique on real scenarios where robust, light-weight, miniaturized and simple to use and cost-effective tools are required by first responders.

Keywords: Gas phase detection, SERS, portable Raman, CWAs, trace level

34 **1. Introduction**

35 The nerve gas attacks with sarin in Matsumoto (1994) and Tokyo (1995) and in the
36 armed conflict in Syria (Goutha 2013 and Khan Shaykhun 2017) are recent and
37 representative examples of the present world threat spectrum. Chemical Warfare Agents
38 (CWAs), initially developed in the First World War, include vesicant and blister agents
39 such as phosgene (PD) and mustard gas (HD) and nerve agents, as sarin (GB) and
40 venomous agent X (VX). The nerve agents are highly toxic due to the irreversible
41 binding with the nerve sites responsible for acetylcholinesterase breakdown, a necessary
42 process in neurotransmission. Sarin gas presents the highest toxicity with a IDLH
43 (Immediately Dangerous to Life or Health) of $0.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. These CWAs are able to
44 spread out in the atmosphere, creating a toxic scenario in few seconds. The early
45 detection and identification of these agents in gas phase is essential for the safety of first
46 responders and for the efficient evacuation of threatened public spaces.

47 Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) is a technique capable of label-free
48 ultrasensitive vibrational “fingerprinting”, and as such it is recognized as highly
49 interesting method for explosive and chemical threat detection [1]. The technique has
50 also become suitable for on-site detection thanks to the development of portable
51 equipment with adequate spectral resolution (ranging from 7 to 12cm^{-1}) and low weight
52 (330 to 2450g) at reasonable prices, ca. 10 thousand euros without spectral library.
53 However there are still several challenges to be overcome before this technique can be
54 implemented as “off-the-shelf” solution for CWA detection.

55 SERS mainly relies on the enhancement of the Raman signal due to the plasmon
56 resonance of a metallic nanostructure. This effect only occurs when the target molecule
57 is in close contact to the metal, and for this reason an interaction i.e. physical or
58 chemical adsorption is required between the molecule and the metal. The magnitude of
59 the enhancement depends on several parameters including composition, size,
60 morphology, topology, surface distribution, and dielectric environment of the metallic
61 nanostructure on substrate surface. Many efforts have been devoted in SERS field for
62 the development of optimum SERS substrates ranging from fancy shapes of
63 nanoparticles with sharp edges to ordered nanostructures whose the shape and spacing
64 was optimized with simulation and then on fabricated in cleanroom. Other key factors

65 for the highly sensitive detection of molecules include the cross-section of the molecule,
66 its stability, interactions with the SERS substrate and its solid, liquid or gaseous state.

67 Most of the SERS applications in the open literature refer to the detection in liquid
68 phase and only few reports for gas phase detection at concentrations below 10 ppmV
69 could be found. Van Duyne and coworkers reported the detection of 8 ppmV of benzene
70 thiol on a SERS substrate consisting of well-ordered silica nanospheres coated with a
71 200 nm thick Ag film [2]. A recyclable surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS)
72 substrate, consisting of Ag nanorods coated with an ultrathin HfO₂ shell (Ag
73 NRs@HfO₂), was able to detect, after 40 minutes exposure, concentrations in the gas
74 phase as low as 20ppb of the molecule 2-Naphthalenethiol (2-NAT). Then substrate was
75 easily regenerated by heating at 250°C for 25 seconds [3]. The SERS detection of
76 volatile organic compounds (VOCs) biomarkers in human breath, such as acetone in the
77 case of diabetes or hydrogen cyanide in patients with cystic fibrosis, is gaining of
78 importance as non-invasive tool in primary screening diagnosis. The group of Boisen
79 detected 5ppmV of hydrogen cyanide in gas phase [4] and later on *P. aeruginosa*
80 cultures [5]. The term of *plasmonic nose* was recently coined for a SERS substrate that
81 consists on a core-shell structure of Ag nanocubes encapsulated in porous metal organic
82 framework MOF, in particular ZIF-8 [6]. The VOCs adsorbed on the porous layer
83 formed a 3D confinement space for the molecules near the plasmonic structure. In this
84 system 200 ppmV of toluene were detected and the detection limit could be lowered to
85 50ppb for 2-nitrotoluene, a molecule with higher cross section. Another recent example
86 of low concentration in gas phase was the detection of 10ppmV of benzene. In this case
87 the strategy for decreasing the detection limit involved deep cooling of the SERS
88 substrate down to -80°C, to promote adsorption and condensation of the molecules [7].
89 Recently, a 3D porous substrate successfully detected for the first time 0.1 ppmV of
90 NO₂ in the gas phase with a hand-held Raman detector [8]. The high surface area
91 employed consisted of a 3D multilayer structure made of Au coated-Ag nanowires
92 (AgNWs) forming lots of random hot spots in the cross points of the fibers. In our
93 laboratory, the detection of 625 ppbV of DMMP, a surrogate molecule of the G-series
94 nerve agents which are of particular concern due to its extreme toxicity and persistence,
95 was recently reported using a substrate consisting of self-assembled AuNPs coated with
96 a citrate layer that acted as an effective trap for the target molecules [9]. The above
97 results illustrate the importance of substrate selection for gas phase using SERS. It must

98 provide high electromagnetic enhancement (EF), but also chemical affinity towards the
99 target molecule while avoiding band interference with the functional groups responsible
100 for this affinity.

101 In this work we selected Ag nanoplates as the plasmonic material to be used in
102 DMMP detection in view of four reasons: i) the optical properties of Ag (real and
103 imaginary parts of the dielectric function), that makes this metal the main candidate to
104 get interesting optical effects, including plasmon resonances [10]; ii) the specific
105 interaction of DMMP with Ag through the P-O bond, as already reported in the first
106 study of DMMP detection in roughened Ag electrodes [11]; iii) the electromagnetic
107 field enhancement at the tips and edges of the nanoplates; and finally, iv) the
108 coincidence of the plasmon resonance band of Ag nanoplates with the excitation laser
109 wavelength used for the Raman measurements, 785nm. We have compared the response
110 of the synthesized Ag nanoplates on three different substrates, SiO₂/Si, stainless steel
111 mesh and graphite foil. The SERS response was analyzed using Rhodamine (R6G) as
112 probe molecule with lasers of $\lambda = 532, 633$ and 785 nm. The same substrates were also
113 studied for the detection of 2.5 ppmV of DMMP in gas phase with a benchtop and
114 portable Raman equipments. The interactions of the DMMP molecule with the Ag
115 surface were simulated using Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations carried out
116 by Gaussian09 quantum chemistry program [12] to explain the relative intensities
117 variation of the characteristic Raman vibrational modes.

118 **2. Materials and methods**

119 **2.1 Materials**

120 Silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99.9999%), sodium citrate tribasic dehydrate (>99%),
121 hydrogen peroxide solution (H₂O₂, 30% wt), potassium bromide (KBr, >99%), sodium
122 borohydride (NaBH₄, >99%), poly(diallyl dimethylammonium (PDDA, 20% wt),
123 rhodamine 6G (99%) and dimethyl methylphosphonate (DMMP, 97%) were purchased
124 from Sigma-Aldrich. All solutions were prepared in distilled water. Acetone and
125 isopropyl alcohol were also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. DMMP vapours were
126 generated using a calibrated permeation tube (MT-PD-Experimental 107-100-7845-
127 HE3-C50, 126.78 ng/min \pm 4.81 ng/min at 80°C) from VALCO.

128

129 **2.2 Preparation of SERS substrates**

130 The Ag nanoplates (Ag nPlates) were synthesized according to a previously reported
131 method [13]. Briefly, in a 20 mL vial, the following aqueous solutions were sequentially
132 added while stirring: H₂O (8.5 mL); AgNO₃ (3.75 mL, 0.5 mM); sodium citrate (1 mL,
133 25 mM); H₂O₂ (28.2 μL); KBr (10 μL, 1 mM). Finally NaBH₄ (1.25 mL, 10 mM) was
134 quickly added to the solution to cause Ag reduction. A colour transition from yellow to
135 blue could be observed in the solution after approximately two minutes, indicating plate
136 formation. Ag nPlates solutions were then centrifuged afterwards for 20 minutes at
137 21,000 rpm, and the supernatant was centrifuged again. The obtained precipitates were
138 resuspended in water and citrate was added to obtain a solution with a final
139 concentration of 80 mg/L of Ag and 2.5 mM of sodium citrate.

140 The Ag nPlates were deployed on three different supports (4mm x 8mm): SiO₂/Si
141 chip (Sil'Tronix 1 μm of wet thermal SiO₂ wafer), stainless steel mesh (see SEM image
142 in Fig. S1) and graphite foil (RivaTherm-HD type from Kempchen). Figure S2 shows
143 digital photographs of the three different supports. Before the deposition the supports
144 were sequentially washed with acetone, isopropanol and water during 10 min each, in
145 an ultrasound bath. After, SERS substrates were immersed in an aqueous solution of
146 PDDA (0.2% v/v) during 4 hours, washed with distilled water and dried for 10 minutes
147 at 100 °C. Finally, the supports were immersed in the Ag nplates suspension overnight
148 and allowed to dry at room temperature, to obtain the SERS substrates. In the case of
149 graphite, before immersing in the PDDA solution the surface was peeled-off with scotch
150 tape. The obtained SERS substrates are denoted as nPlates@SiO₂/Si, Ag nPlates@SS
151 and Ag nPlates@graphite for the remainder of this work.

152 **2.3 Material Characterization**

153 Size distribution and morphology of Ag nPlates were studied by TEM (FEI Tecnai
154 T200). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained using a FEG
155 INSPECT 50. Five SEM images of each SERS substrates after coating were analysed to
156 assess the Ag nPlates density on the surface using ImageJ analysis software. A UV-Vis
157 Spectrophotometer Varian Cary 50 Spectrometer was used to measure the absorbance
158 properties of Ag nPlates in solution and Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) spectra of
159 the Ag nPlates coated on a glass substrate following the same protocol described above
160 for the other substrates. The measurements of the UV-Vis absorption spectra for the Ag
161 nPlates coated on a stainless steel mesh and graphite substrate were performed in a

162 Jasco V-670 spectrometer equipped with a diffuse reflectance chamber. The
163 measurements of the solid surfaces were allways obtained with white BaSO₄ as
164 reference for the background.

165 **2.4 Raman Spectroscopy for characterization of SERS substrates.**

166 An Alpha 300 Raman spectrometer of WITec was used with a confocal optical
167 microscope (480nm as lateral spatial resolution, 2 cm⁻¹ spectral resolution). Raman-
168 SERS spectra were collected in backscattering geometry. Excitation of the samples was
169 carried out with lasers 532nm, 633nm and 785 nm at room temperature and applying a
170 irradiance of 0.13 mW/μm², 0.67 mW/μm² and 0.88 mW/μm², respectively.

171 The analytical enhancement factor (AEF) [14], of the different substrates, was
172 calculated according to equation (1). R6G was selected as probe molecule monitoring
173 its C-C stretching mode displaced at 1512 cm⁻¹.

$$AEF = \frac{\frac{I_{SERS}}{C_{SERS}}}{\frac{I_{Raman}}{C_{Raman}}} \quad (1)$$

174 Where C_{Raman} and C_{SERS} are the R6G concentration in the Raman measurements and
175 SERS conditions, respectively. And I_{Raman} and I_{SERS} are the normalized intensity values
176 (cts·mW⁻¹·s⁻¹) of the 1512 cm⁻¹ band for normal Raman and SERS measurements, respectively.

177 A droplet of 2μL aqueous solution R6G 10 μM was deposited on the SERS
178 substrate and dried under ambient conditions. The R6G spectrum of the SERS substrate
179 was measured in ten different points of the dried droplet and the intensity of the peak at
180 1512 cm⁻¹ was averaged. The normal Raman R6G spectrum was measured focusing the
181 laser beam, 633 nm and 785 nm, in the aqueous solution R6G 1 mM. For the 532 nm
182 laser line, the R6G droplet was dried before acquisition to avoid fluorescence effects.

183 **2.5 Experimental set-up for gas phase measurements**

184 SERS experiments for detecting DMMP in gas phase were conducted in a gas cell
185 (2.7x10⁻² cm³), where a gas stream, 10ml STP/min, containing 2.5 ppmV (14 mg/m³) of
186 DMMP in nitrogen was fed continuously. DMMP vapours were generated using a
187 calibrated permeation tube as described in our previous work [9]. Two Raman
188 equipments were used: the benchtop equipment described above (Alpha 300 Raman
189 spectrometer, WITec) and a portable Raman BWTEK i-Raman pro system (6 cm⁻¹

190 spectral resolution). In the latter case, an excitation wavelength of 785nm with a power
191 laser of 280 mW ($0.035 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}^2$), 1s of integration time and averaging 100 spectra
192 were used for all the measurements. A schematic drawing together with a picture of the
193 set-up with the portable Raman and the gas cell for measurements are presented in Fig.
194 1.

196 **Fig. 1.** a) Scheme of the experimental set-up used for detection of CWA vapours. b) Digital
197 photograph of the real set-up including the portable Raman and the microfluidic gas chamber.

198 2.6 DFT calculations

199 Geometry optimizations and frequency analysis calculations for the
200 organophosphorous compound and Ag atoms were undertaken using DFT methods. All
201 the calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 [12] software package.

202 The ground state geometries were optimized employing the density functional
203 theory (DFT) [15,16] with the B3LYP hybrid functional (Becke's gradient-corrected
204 exchange correlation in conjunction with the Lee–Yang–Parr correlation functional with
205 three parameters) and the 6-311++G(d,p) one-electron atomic basis sets. The adsorbed
206 DMMP molecules and the Ag atoms were calculated with the 6-311++G(d,p) basis set
207 and the LANL2DZ basis set considering a pseudo potential, respectively.

208 3. Results and Discussion

209 3.1 Characterization of SERS substrates

210 The synthesis of the Ag nPlates was reproducible and in all the cases the UV-Vis
211 spectrum (Fig. 2a) displayed the main broad band at around 700nm, assigned to the in-
212 plane dipole plasmon resonance. The other two LSPR bands at 460 nm and 331 nm are

213 assigned to the in-plane quadrupole and out-of-plane quadrupole plasmon resonances of
 214 triangular nanoplates, respectively [17]. We observed that during storage at room
 215 temperature and in the darkness, the peak intensity progressively decreased and blue
 216 shifted to 640 nm after 30 days (see Fig. 2 a). The Localize Surface Plasmon Resonance
 217 (LSPR) is very dependent on the shape and size of the nanoparticles, and this evolution
 218 is probably caused by surface atomic migration within the Ag nPlate that evolves
 219 towards more thermodynamically stable forms [18]. In our case this involves a
 220 progressive smoothing of the plates, since the round shape (111), is more stable than
 221 tips (110) in triangular shape. The analysis of TEM images for freshly made samples
 222 (Fig. 2b) shows a mixture of Ag nanoparticles and nanoplates resulting in an average
 223 yield of 85% to plates with an edge of 38 ± 15 nm ($N > 500$).

224

225 **Fig 2.** a) UV Vis spectra of aqueous solution containing Ag nPlates: evolution with time during
 226 storage. Insert: digital photograph of Ag nanoplates solution. TEM image of synthesized Ag
 227 nanoplates: b) freshly made and c) aged 30 days. Scale bar 100 nm.

228 The SEM images presented in Fig. 3 show a homogeneous distribution of the Ag
 229 nPlates deposited on different surfaces. The analysis of the SEM images resulted in a
 230 similar surface coverage for the three substrates $42 \pm 5\%$ (SiO_2/Si chip), $41 \pm 5\%$
 231 (stainless steel mesh) and $44 \pm 3\%$ (graphite foil) These values are higher than the 30%
 232 coverage that we previously found with Au NPs deposited on SiO_2/Si surfaces [9]. This
 233 could be attributed to the planar structure of the Ag nanoplates, versus the spherical Au
 234 nanoparticles. It is also possible to observe densely packed aggregates of nanoplates,

235 resulting in close contact of their edges that will result in couplings between LSPRs of
236 the metallic nanoplates [19]. The UV-Vis spectrum for the Ag nanoplates deposited on the
237 glass substrate broadens and the maximum is blue shifted compared to the nanoplate
238 solution (see Fig. S3). This observation could be attributed to the differences in the
239 dielectric permittivity either of the propagating media of the light, changing from water
240 in the liquid solution to air in the case of the coated substrates [20] or differences in the
241 differences in the properties of underlying substrates [21,22]. The broadening of the
242 spectrum favors the coupling of the plasmon with the different lasers and specially with
243 the 785nm due to the blue shifting observed. In the case of the non-transparent
244 substrates stainless steel and graphite, the diffuse reflectance UV-Vis spectra (Figure
245 S3) showed an increase in the absorption band of the coated substrates in the region
246 above 700nm corresponding to the SPR of the silver plates.

247

248 **Fig. 3.** SEM images of Ag nanoplates deposited on these SERS substrates: a) SiO₂/Si; b)
249 stainless steel mesh; c) graphite foil. Insert scale 50 nm.

250 The three substrates were first characterized with R6G as a probe molecule with
251 three different lasers 532, 633 and 785 nm. The as collected spectra, without any
252 modifications (i.e. baseline corrections and smoothing) are presented in Fig. 4. It is
253 immediately apparent that the highest intensity and lower signal to noise ratio for R6G
254 it is observed for the 532 nm laser. The Raman intensity depends on the molecules
255 under study and, when the analyte is a chromophore, close in energy to the frequency of
256 the excitation, resonant Raman scattering (RRS) occurs. The RRS intensities can be 10⁶
257 larger than normal (off-resonance) Raman intensities [10], in this case we should called
258 the technique SERRS instead of just SERS. When the molecule is adsorbed on the
259 surface of the metal, the strong fluorescence of R6G, is quenched to a certain extent due
260 to non-radiative interactions with the metal surface. When comparing the raw data of
261 the spectra at 532 nm, for the three different substrates (Fig. 4a), the fluorescence of

262 R6G could be observed as a broad band in the spectrum, centered at around 600 cm^{-1} . The
263 quenching of this signal is clearly more effective for the case of the graphite substrate. It
264 has been reported that not only graphene, but also other carbonaceous materials could
265 be considered as good SER(R)S substrates due to resonance effect and quenching
266 fluorescence either via charge transfer or energy transfer [23]. In fact, for the SiO_2/Si
267 substrate, the one with the lowest conductivity (10^{-1} S/m) we observed the lowest EF
268 and SERS gain (Fig. 4) for all the wavelengths tested.

269 In the case of the excitation with the 633 nm laser, where the energy of the laser is
270 still near to the excitation of the chromophore, we can still observe the R6G spectra
271 although with lower intensities for the three supports (Fig. 4b). In the case of 785nm
272 laser line, this wavelength matches with the plasmon resonance of the Ag nPlates (see
273 Fig. 2 and Fig. S3), and the spectrum of the R6G molecule could only clearly
274 distinguished for the graphite support (Fig. 4c), most probably due to charge transfer
275 from the electrons of the plasmonic metal to the graphite. The easily available, low cost
276 graphite material could be an alternative support for the deposition of active SERS
277 nanostructures being capable of making an additional contribution to the enhancement
278 of the signal by different mechanisms, including fluorescence quenching, charge and
279 energy transfer and also probably resonant effects of this support. This is in accordance
280 with the observations presented by Sil et al. [23] for different carbonaceous materials
281 (charcoal, graphite, MWCNT and GO).

282 From averaging 10 different spots in each experimental condition (excitation
283 wavelength and substrate), the analytical enhancement factor (AEF) was calculated
284 (Fig. 4d). In the three studied substrates at the excitation wavelength of 785nm reports
285 the highest analytical enhancement factor was obtained, even for the spectra on Ag
286 nPlates@ SiO_2/Si and Ag nPlates@SS that is less defined. This result is due to the low
287 signal of R6G in Raman conditions (I_{Raman}) under excitation wavelength of 785 nm. Fig.
288 S4 shows the Raman spectrum of R6G 1mM under the three excitation wavelengths.

289

290

291 **Fig. 4.** Raman spectra of R6G 10⁻⁵M droplet dried on three different SERS substrates: Ag
 292 nPlates@SiO₂/Si, Ag nPlates@SS and Ag nPlates@graphite for different excitation
 293 wavelengths: a) 532 nm: b) 633 nm and c) 785nm. d) Analytical EF (AEF) calculated for the
 294 three SERS substrates and for different excitation wavelengths (532, 633 and 785 nm). For
 295 better visualization in a) and c) spectra have been vertically translated.

296 3.2 CWAs gas phase detection capabilities of the SERS substrates

297 The SERS substrates were also tested for the measurement of the simulant nerve
 298 agent DMMP in gas phase in the benchtop equipment using the 785nm laser and
 299 graphite substrate, which resulted in the highest AEF. Furthermore in the case of using
 300 633nm and 785nm with SiO₂/Si and stainless steel mesh substrates, it was not possible
 301 to get a spectrum. As soon as the laser was focused on the sample, the DMMP
 302 molecules were decomposed and a broad band in the region 1450 to 1700 cm⁻¹,
 303 corresponding to amorphous carbon was observed. This phenomenon is attributed to the
 304 photo-thermal decomposition of the DMMP molecules adsorbed on the enhancing metal
 305 surface [24].

306 The Raman spectrum for neat liquid DMMP and the SERS spectra on Ag
307 nPlates@graphite for a concentration of 2.5ppmV DMMP in the gas phase are
308 presented in Fig. 5a and Fig 5b for benchtop and portable Raman equipments,
309 respectively. First of all, it is important to note that the fingerprint of the DMMP
310 molecule is observed with both detectors. However the relative intensity of the
311 characteristic bands differs from the acquired at normal Raman conditions. The Raman
312 spectra recorded by the portable equipment on randomly selected spots are presented in
313 Fig. 5b. Due to the lower resolution of the portable equipment, 6 cm^{-1} , compared to 2
314 cm^{-1} in the benchtop equipment, the bands are broader and could be also slightly
315 shifted. This is clearly observed for the main band of the DMMP liquid measured in
316 both equipments. It is important to note that the spectra were reproducible in all the
317 randomly selected spots, showing three distinctive bands, with similar intensities and
318 assigned to PO_3 , P-C stretching and PO_2 bending (for more details see Table 1). This
319 allowed a clear identification of the DMMP using the hand held instruments, for a gas
320 phase concentration of 2.5 ppmV.

321 Fig. 6a shows the molecular structures of the two investigated DMMP-Ag
322 complexes. The most stable Ag-DMMP geometry, among studied, corresponds with
323 DMMP molecule adsorbed on 6 Ag atoms (in blue) though P=O group. A less-stable
324 Ag-DMMP* complex resulting from DMMP approximation of the phosphate group that
325 looks like an umbrella, $(\text{PO}_3)_{\text{umbrella}}$ is also plotted.

326 Fig. 6b compiles the simulated Raman spectra of DMMP molecule and DMMP-Ag
327 complexes. Comparing with the most significant bands from experimental SERS spectra
328 (see Fig. 5 and Table 1), simulated Raman spectra show similar bands, although
329 changes in both relative intensities and the position of the bands are clearly noticed.
330 Bands at 504 and 715 cm^{-1} assigned to $(\text{PO}_3)_{\text{umbrella}}$ bending and to $(\text{P}-\text{CH}_3)$ stretching +
331 $(\text{P}-\text{O})$ stretching + $(\text{P}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3)$ bending, respectively, are slightly displaced to around
332 483 and 672 cm^{-1} (for more details see Table 1). The ratio between these two simulated
333 bands (Intensity at 672 cm^{-1} / Intensity at 483 cm^{-1}) for DMMP molecule and Ag-
334 DMMP (P=O) complex is the same. However, the simulated spectrum for Ag-DMMP*
335 (PO_3) shows an increment in this ratio, similar to the one observed experimentally. This
336 could provide some insight on the adsorption dynamics of DMMP molecules on Ag
337 plates under experimental conditions. Although less energetically favored, this
338 geometry is contributing to the dynamic SERS response. However, it should be noticed

339 that for simplicity the simulation considers one DMMP molecule and 6 silver atoms
 340 while experimentally, a molecule of DMMP may interact not only with several silver
 341 atoms but also with other DMMP molecules, increasing the possibilities of (PO₃)_{umbrella}
 342 – Ag interactions.

343

344 **Fig 5.** Raman spectra of DMMP liquid and DMMP in vapour phase (2.5 ppmV, 14 mg/m³)
 345 measured on Ag nplates@graphite using: a) the benchtop equipment and b) the portable
 346 equipment. For the portable equipment five different spectra for vapours detection are shown,
 347 measured at different random spots on the support, together with the spectrum of Ag
 348 nPlates@graphite. (a-b) Excitation wavelength 785 nm; grey shadows indicate bands assigned
 349 to DMMP (more information in Table 1).

350 **Table 1.** Tentative assignments of the experimental Raman and SERS bands for DMMP pure
 351 liquid and vapor on Ag nPlates@graphite, together with calculated values by DFT simulations.

Band	Raman Shift of DMMP vibrational modes (cm ⁻¹)				Tentative assignment [25]
	Pure liquid Experimental	Calculated DMMP in vacuum	DMMP Vapors on Ag nPlates@graphite: Benchtop equipment	Calculated Ag- DMMP (PO ₃)	
a	504	483	515	469	Bending PO ₃
b	715	672	710	663	Stretching PC
c	794	756	814	756 (weak)	Bending PO ₂
d	825	791	845	785	Bending PO ₂

352

353

354 **Fig. 6.** a) Optimized geometries for the DMMP in vacuum (i) and adsorbed on six Ag atoms
 355 according to the following possibilities: (ii) anchoring through the three oxygen atoms
 356 of DMMP (PO₃) and (iii) interaction via P=O group. b) Calculated spectra of DMMP
 357 (i) and DMMP-Ag complexes considering de adsorption of DMMP on three silver
 358 atoms through: (ii) the three oxygens (PO₃) and (iii) P=O group. Grey shadows
 359 indicate bands assigned to DMMP (more information in Table 1).

360 To evaluate the reproducibility of the Ag nplates@graphite fabrication method,
 361 three different Ag nplates@graphite substrates were prepared, and the SERS spectra
 362 (2.5ppmV DMMP) were collected randomly in ten different spots. Figure 7a shows the
 363 average peak intensity at 712 cm⁻¹ of DMMP, showing an average relative standard
 364 deviation (RSD) for the SERS intensity of 5%. This value indicates the good
 365 reproducibility of fabrication method and also the detection capabilities of Ag
 366 nPlates@graphite substrates.

367 Finally, we further evaluate the concept of SERS sensor for rapid CWAs detection
 368 in gas phase. Figure 7b shows the intensity evolution of DMMP, monitoring peak
 369 displayed at 712 cm⁻¹, as a function of exposure time to the vapours of this gas. It is
 370 important to note that the response time $t_{50\%}$ defined as the time to reach 50% or 90% of
 371 the final Raman intensity, is $t_{50\%}=137s$ and $t_{90\%}$ is only 261s. This value is outstanding
 372 compared to the early work for detection of DMMP in gas phase that needed 40 minutes
 373 exposure to acquire a meaningful spectrum with the benchtop equipment available at
 374 that time. This time is slightly higher than the response time that we found in our
 375 previous study with benchtop equipment [9]. It is also important to note that due to the
 376 lower resolution of the handheld equipment, the acquisition time is higher (100s)
 377 compared to (1s) in benchtop equipment. Although it is difficult to compare detection
 378 values for different conditions, molecules and equipment's, the relevance of the
 379 obtained results it is presented in Table 2 with the available literature data for gas phase

380 detection at concentrations below 10 ppm. These results demonstrate the high quality of
381 Ag nplates@graphite as SERS sensors of gas molecules, combined with handheld
382 equipment for real applications on field.

383

384 **Fig. 7.** a) The reproducibility of the Ag nplates@graphite: average intensity of the peak at 712
385 cm^{-1} of DMMP (2.5 ppmV) of three different Ag nplates@graphite. The error bars indicate
386 standard deviation. b) Intensity value of the peak at 712 cm^{-1} of DMMP as a function of
387 exposure time to 2.5 ppmV. Both experiments were carried out with the portable Raman
388 equipment.

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396 **Table 2.** Literature review for gas phase detection of different molecules, at concentrations
 397 below 10ppm, with SERS as detection technology.

Material	Target molecule	Raman equipment	Limit of detection	Detection time	Ref.
Ag nPlates@graphite	DMMP	Portable	2.5 ppmV	137 s	This work
Cool Ag nanorods	Benzene	Portable	10 ppmV	2 min	[7]
Ag@silica nanospheres	Benzene thiol (BT)	Portable	8 ppmV	50-100 s	[2]
Au-Ag nanowires	NO ₂	Portable	100 ppbV	3 min	[8]
Ag nanorods@HfO ₂	2-naphtalenethiol	Portable	20 ppbV	40 min	[3]
Gold nanopillars	Hydrogen cyanine	Benchtop	5 ppmV	15 min	[5]
AuNP@citrate	DMMP	Benchtop	625 ppbV	120s	[9]
Ag nanocubes@ZIF8	2-nitrotoluene	Benchtop	50 ppbV	15 min	[6]

398

399 **4. Conclusions**

400 The effect of different substrates (SiO₂/Si, stainless steel mesh and graphite foil), where
 401 plasmonic silver nanoplates were deposited, on the SERS signal, with three lasers
 402 ($\lambda=532, 633$ and 785nm) has been evaluated with two molecules R6G in liquid and
 403 DMMP, 2.5ppmV in gas phase. It has been demonstrated that graphite is the best choice
 404 because of efficient quenching of the fluorescent signal ($\lambda=532$ and 633nm), via charge
 405 transfer or energy transfer. This energy transfer is also important when working with the
 406 785nm laser line, with its wavelength matching the plasmon resonance of the silver
 407 nanoplates. In this case a clear spectrum of R6G could be only distinguished on graphite
 408 support. When working with DMMP, it was only possible to use the 785nm laser in
 409 combination with graphite, otherwise the high energy concentrated on the sample
 410 during measurement decomposed the adsorbed DMMP molecules. The interactions of
 411 the DMMP molecule with the silver surface modify the intensities and positions of the
 412 vibrational Raman bands. DFT simulations suggest such variations by the formation of
 413 Ag-DMMP complexes via the PO₃ umbrella. The SERS measurements carried out in
 414 different prepared samples with the handheld Raman equipment for 2.5 ppmV in gas
 415 phase showed a fast response and reproducible fingerprint of the molecule and relative

416 standard deviation of SERS intensity signal of 5%, paving the way for on field
417 applications.

418 **Conflict of interest:**

419 Authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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Supporting Information

Gas phase detection of Chemical Warfare Agents

CWAs with portable Raman

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Figure S1.

Figure S1. SEM image of the stainless steel mesh used as SERS substrate support.

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Figure S2.

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549 **Figure S2.** Digital photographs of the three different supports used as SERS substrate:

550 a) SiO₂/Si chip; b) stainless steel mesh and c) graphite foil. Rule in centimeters (cm).

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Figure S3.

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558 **Figure S3.** UV-Vis spectra of deposited Ag nanoplates on (a) glass; (b) Ag nPlates@SS
559 Mesh and (c) graphite. The spectra of mesh and graphite before incorporating Ag
560 nPlates are also plotted.

561

Figure S4.

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564 **Figure S4.** Raman spectra of Rhodamine 6G (R6G, 1mM) measured under the three different
565 excitation wavelengths: a) 532nm; b) 633nm and c) 785nm. Grey shadow indicates vibrational
566 mode selected for AEF calculations: PC stretching around 1512 cm⁻¹.

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